

Retrospective Observational Research Comparing the Results of Non-Operative and Surgical Treatment for Displaced Clavicle Fracture

Kumuda Bandhu Sahoo¹, Braja Sundar Sahoo², Laba Kumar Naik³

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Orthopaedics, VSSIMSAR, Burla, Sambalpur, Odisha, India

²Associate Professor, Department of Orthopaedics, VSSIMSAR, Burla, Sambalpur, Odisha, India

³Assistant Professor, Department of Orthopaedics, VSSIMSAR, Burla, Sambalpur, Odisha, India

Received: 25-11-2022 / Revised: 25-12-2022 / Accepted: 05-01-2023

Corresponding author: Laba Kumar Naik

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract

Introduction: Conservative care has been used for ages to treat clavicle fractures. Clavicle fractures seldom fail to heal, and they were formerly thought to primarily have radiological significance. The situation has altered, and operational treatment is now preferred for reasons of union, cosmesis, and quick recovery. Both approaches are contrasted while taking into account the patient's happiness, early recovery, cosmesis, and functional results.

Method: 90 patients with displaced clavicle fractures (AO B1 & B2) in total were split into two groups: non-surgical and operational. Voluntary informed consent was given. The cost, process, results and complications of both modalities were presented to the patient. The trial was conducted until 45 patients were included in each group, after which the patient was assigned to Group I (conservative) or Group II (operative). Patients in both groups underwent follow-up exams at 5, 2, and 8 months utilising their subjective assessments, DASH scores, ranges of mobility, radiological evaluations, and any complications that may have arisen.

Result: All 90 patients ranged in age from 21 to 65, with a mean age of 34.4 years. Twenty (65.6%) of the conservative group's participants and 25 (74.1%) of the group that underwent surgery exhibited dominant side involvement. Compared to the operational group, the non-operative group experienced higher complications. At 5 weeks and 2 months, Group II's DASH score was higher than that of Group I. The overall satisfaction rate for non-surgical patients was 20 (62.83%), whereas the satisfaction rate for operational patients was 27 (81%) and 7 (21%) respectively. A follow-up period of 8.4 months on average was used (5-17 months).

Conclusion: Even though operative treatment offers advantages over non-operative treatment in terms of early mobilization, union, absence of mal-union, and cosmetic acceptance, it also has drawbacks that should be considered when deciding between the two modalities. When it comes to patient satisfaction with regard to functional results, conservative treatment is crucial for underprivileged individuals.

Keywords: Clavicle fracture, AO B1 & B2, Displaced fracture, Conservative Treatment, Non-operative treatment, Operative treatment, Clavicular plate.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Clavicle fractures occur frequently, accounting for 2.6% of all fractures and 44% of shoulder girdle fractures [2, 3]. Up to 80% of clavicle fractures occur at the middle shaft, making it the most common site [1,4]. The transitional alteration of the clavicle's lateral curve, which is covered by muscles and medially relatively exposed bone, is what causes mid shaft involvement [3]. Since non-union of a clavicle fracture is rare and has been proven to be as low as 0.12-08% with conservative therapy, the clavicle fracture has been managed conservatively for years. Mal-union was thought to be significant in radiography. In particular, cases where the initial shortening of the bone is greater than 20 mm, a recent study found that non-union of clavicle fractures can be as high as 10-15% [5]. In research by Hill et al., which included 242 patients, 66 (27%) of whom had displaced clavicle fractures, it was found that 15% of these instances did not heal. 25% had mild to moderate pain. Of 52 patients who were available for follow-up, 28 complained about their appearance [5]. Both union and bone length are related to the functional and aesthetic outcome. According to Eskola et al., patients with bone shortening of more than 15 mm experienced severe pain [2].

The clavicle serves as a strut to maintain the upper limb away from the trunk and transmits forces from the upper limb to the trunk, therefore a displaced fracture of the clavicle may cause a poor functional outcome and cosmetic deformity as well as non-union or mal-union [7-9]. The therapy of clavicle fractures is therefore swinging more in favor of surgical intervention, but surgical intervention has its drawbacks, including the high cost of care (especially in developing nations), infection, anesthesia-related complications, and injury to the nerve and vascular tissue. Fortunately, injuries to major nerves are

quite uncommon, except injuries to the supraclavicular nerve, which have a 10–29% incidence rate [7-9] and result in cutaneous hypoesthesia in the infraclavicular region as high as 55.3% [10]. Thus, there is no universally accepted approach to treating clavicle fractures.

This research analyzes the patient-oriented results of non-operative and surgical treatment for clavicle fractures.

Method:

This retrospective cohort research was carried out in the Department of Orthopaedics, VSSIMSAR, Burla, Sambalpur, Odisha between the months of February 2020 and November 2021. After receiving approval from the regional research and ethical review board, patients with displaced fractures of the middle shaft of the clavicle were enrolled in the study. 90 patients with displaced clavicle fractures (AO B1 & B2) were split into two groups: Group I (conservative) and Group II (operative).

Inclusion Criteria:

- i. Age: Must be at least 18 years old
- ii. Open mid-shaft fracture
- iii. There was no medical issue with general anesthesia (in the case of surgery)
- iv. Reduction of > 16 mm in radiograph (shaft width)

Exclusion Criteria:

- i. Pathological fracture
- ii. compound fracture
- iii. A fracture in both clavicles
- iv. Patient with shoulder morbidities
- v. Patient with many traumas
- vi. Fracture older than two months
- vii. Clavicle segmental fracture
- viii. Fracture with neurovascular damage
- ix. Fracture with damage to the coracoclavicular ligament

Voluntary informed consent was given. The patient was informed about both modalities, their procedures, costs, outcomes, and potential complications. Following the patient's decision, he was assigned to Group I (conservative) and Group II (operative). 45 patients from each group were eventually enrolled in the trial.

Conservative Group: 45 patients in this group received ipsilateral arm slings and traditional clavicular braces or figure-8 bandages as treatment.

Operative Group: S-shaped locking clavicular plates were used to diagnose and treat these individuals. The procedure was done 5-7 days after the injury. Under general anaesthesia, the patient was lying on his back with a towel folded across his shoulders. Painting was done in a strictly aseptic environment. At the fracture site, a transverse incision was planned along the clavicle. The supraclavicular nerve was preserved after being dissected. The fracture location was exposed and decreased when the soft tissue was dissected. The clavicular plates were fixed using locking S-shaped plates. To fix the fragments, at least two screws were inserted on either side of the fracture. When necessary, inter-fragmentary lag screws were employed. Over a suction drain, the wound was layer by layer closed.

Following surgery, an arm pouch or arm sling was supplied. After five days, surgical patients were released. The day after surgery, the non-operative cases were released. After seven days, the operated cases required suture removal, and movements were then gradually reintroduced as the pain permitted. However, the patients in both groups underwent follow-up at 5 weeks, 2 months, and 5 months utilising the patients' subjective assessments, DASH scores, range of motion, radiological examination, and complications, if any.

Results

The primary reason for avoiding surgery was the cost of the procedure, despite the fact that all patients were given the opportunity and explanation of the benefits and drawbacks of both conservative and surgical methods.

All 90 patients ranged in age from 21 to 65, with a mean age of 34.4 years. In the non-operative group, there were 34 (71.5%) men and 11 (29%) women, whereas there were 39 (81%) men and 6 (21%) women in the operational group. In the entire study, there were 73 men (75.8%) and 17 women (24.2%). All of the fractures in the conservative group (20 (65.7%) and the surgical group (26 (74.1%) showed dominant side involvement (**Table 1**).

Table 1: General and clinical demographics of the patients

Characteristics	No. of Patients
Mean Age (years)	34.4 years
Conservative Group	
Characteristics	No. of Patients (%)
Male	34 (71.3%)
Female	11 (29%)
Operative group	
Male	39 (81%)
Female	6 (19%)
A fracture involving dominant side	
Conservative group	20
Operative group	25
The average time taken to heal	
Conservative group	15.2 weeks
Operative group	11.74 weeks

The clavicular brace or figure-of-seven bandage was applied right away in the non-operative group while the recovery period after surgery ranged from 2 to 14 days. It took 11 days for the wound to heal (11-14 days).

In non-operative cases, the average time to union was 15.2 (11-29) weeks. (**Table 2**).

Table 2: Time taken in Non-operative group

Categories	No. of patients
Non-union	2 (8.74%)
Mal-union	14 (42.7%)
Muscle wasting	4 (14.1%)
upper limb pressure symptoms cases	3 (11.3%)
shoulder stiffness	1 (5.70%)
pain after union	7 (22.84%)
cosmetic abnormality	6 (21%)

In the non-operative group, there were 2 (8.74%) non-union cases, 14 (42.7%) mal-union cases, 4 (14.1%) muscle wasting cases, 3 (11.3%) upper limb pressure symptoms cases, 1 (5.70%) shoulder stiffness cases (recovered with physiotherapy), and 7 (22.84%) patients complaining of pain after union (all of

these had marked shortening of clavicle >16mm). From the 14 cases of mal-union, only 6 (21%) patients complained of a cosmetic abnormality, but they were all happy with the union and the outcome's functional results.

The average time taken to union was 11.74 (9-21) weeks (**Table 3**).

Categories	No. of patients
mal-union	1 (4.3%)
implant removal due to infection	3 (5.6%)
Hardware protrusion and irritation	4 (14.27%)
implant removal	5 (11.41%)
unsightly surgical scars	8 (21%)
infraclavicular hypoesthesia	5 (16.13%)

There was only one (4.3%) mal-union in the operated group, and all cases united. 3 patients (5.6%) required implant removal due to infection. Hardware protrusion and irritation were reported by 4 (14.27%) patients. Overall, 5 patients (11.41%) required implant removal. 8 (21%) patients reported having unsightly surgical scars. 5 patients (16.13%) reported postoperative infraclavicular hypoesthesia, which in most cases improved over time.

At 5 weeks and 2 months, Group II's DASH score was higher than that of Group I. In the non-surgical group, 20 (62.84%) patients were generally satisfied, while 6 (21%) partially satisfied patients and 5

(17.13%) were not. In the operative group, 25 (81%) patients were satisfied, while 8 (21%) were not. The typical time to follow up was 8.6 months (5-17 months).

Discussion:

The fractured clavicle was treated conservatively for many years due to the extremely low incidence of non-union (0.2-0.9%) and mal-union being of only radiological consequence. After that, no other studies have produced these findings [11]. Recent research, however, shown that mal-union and non-union rates between 10% and 15% result with subpar cosmetic and functional outcomes [12]. As a result, operative therapy is now the

preferred method [6, 7]. The clavicular plate is now frequently used to treat fractures of the displaced clavicle. 70% of cases involve a dominant side. The fractured clavicle was treated conservatively for many years due to the extremely low incidence of non-union (0.2-0.9%) and mal-union being of only radiological consequence. After that, no other studies have produced these findings (11). Recent research, however, shown that mal-union and non-union rates between 10% and 15% result with subpar cosmetic and functional outcomes [12]. As a result, operative therapy is now the preferred method [6,7]. The clavicular plate is now frequently used to treat fractures of the displaced clavicle. 70% of cases involve a dominant side. [13]

In the conservative group, union took an average of 15.2 weeks, whereas in the operative group, it took an average of 11.74 weeks. In the conservative group, there were 2 (8.74%) cases of non-union and 42.7% of cases demonstrated mal-union, while there were none in the operative group. However, 4.27 percent of the surgical group developed infections, and 4.27 percent of the patients suffered hardware prominence and irritation [17]. 13% of patients in the surgical group reported postoperative infraclavicular hypoesthesia. While 21% of surgery patients have complained about unsightly scars. The other problem in the conservative group is muscular atrophy, pressure symptoms brought on by clavicular braces or figure-seven bandages, and shoulder stiffness that was treated with physiotherapy. In group II, the DASH score was superior. In the conservative group, 62.84% of cases were ultimately satisfied, 17.13% were somewhat satisfied, and 21% were not, whereas in the operative group, 81% of cases were ultimately satisfied and 21% were not. Cost was the primary consideration for choosing non-operative treatment.

Conclusion:

Even though operative treatment offers advantages over non-operative treatment in terms of early mobilization, union, absence of mal-union, and cosmetic acceptance, it also has drawbacks that should be considered when deciding between the two modalities. When it comes to patient satisfaction with regard to functional results, conservative treatment is crucial for underprivileged individuals.

Reference:

1. Sheehan SE, Gaviola G, Sacks A, Gordon R, Shi LL, Smith SE. Traumatic shoulder injuries: a force mechanism analysis of complex injuries to the shoulder girdle and proximal humerus. *American Journal of Roentgenology*. 2013 Sep; 201(3): W409-24.
2. Eskola A, Vainionpää S, Myllynen P, Päätiälä H, Rokkanen P. Outcome of clavicular fracture in 89 patients. *Archives of orthopaedic and traumatic surgery*. 1986 Oct;105(6):337-8.
3. Craig EV. Fractures of the clavicle. *The shoulder*. 1998:428-82.
4. ALLMAN JR FL. Fractures and ligamentous injuries of the clavicle and its articulation. *JBJS*. 1967 Jun 1; 49(4):774-84.
5. Rasmussen JV, Jensen SL, Petersen JB, Falstie-Jensen T, Lausten G, Olsen BS. A retrospective study of the association between shortening of the clavicle after fracture and the clinical outcome in 136 patients. *Injury*. 2011 Apr 1;42(4):414-7.
6. Vickers NJ. Animal communication: when i'm calling you, will you answer too? *Current biology*. 2017 Jul 24; 27(14):R713-5.
7. Society CO. Nonoperative treatment compared with plate fixation of displaced midshaft clavicular fractures. A multicenter, randomized clinical trial.
8. McKee MD, Pedersen EM, Jones C, Stephen DJ, Kreder HJ, Schemitsch EH, Wild LM, Potter J. Deficits

- following nonoperative treatment of displaced midshaft clavicular fractures. *JBJS*. 2006 Jan 1;88(1):35-40.
9. Wang T, Sun JY, Zha GC, Dong SJ, Zhao XJ. Mid-term results of total hip arthroplasty using polyethylene-ceramic composite (Sandwich) liner. *Indian Journal of Orthopaedics*. 2016 Feb;50(1):10-5.
 10. Wang L, Ang M, Lee KT, Naidu G, Kwek EB. Cutaneous hypoesthesia following plate fixation in clavicle fractures. *Indian Journal of Orthopaedics*. 2014 Feb;48(1):10-3.
 11. Rowe CR. 4 An Atlas of Anatomy and Treatment of Midclavicular Fractures. *Clinical Orthopaedics and Related Research (1976-2007)*. 1968 May 1; 58:29-42.
 12. Eskola A, Valnionpää S, Myllynen P, Päätiälä H, Rokkanen P. Surgery for ununited clavicular fracture. *Acta orthopaedica Scandinavica*. 1986 Jan 1;57(4):366-7.
 13. Pyar K. P., Hla S. A., Lwin K. T. Y., Aung Z. N. H., Myat K., Maung L. M., Hein Y. M., Aung L. H., Thant M. M., Maung M. M., Zaw M. H., Mg Y. H. ., Maung N. L., Win T., Mg K. T., Phone S. S., Ya K. Z., Kyaw A. P., Aung Z. P., Kyaw M. T., Min S., Moe T. A., Oo K. M., & Ko M. K. Clinical and laboratory predictors for acquiring COVID-19 infections in patients on maintenance hemodialysis in 5th wave of epidemic in Myanmar. *Journal of Medical Research and Health Sciences*. 2022; 5(12): 2345–2354.